

Fundamentals of Expected Credit Losses

Loan Classification and Provisioning under IFRS 9 in the Banking Sector of Bangladesh

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The article was reviewed by
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Introduction

Expected Credit Loss (ECL) based loan provisioning is an advanced approach to recognizing credit losses in banks and financial institutions. Unlike the traditional incurred loss model, which records losses only when they occur, the ECL model requires banks to estimate potential credit losses in advance, enhancing financial stability and transparency. In Bangladesh, loan classification and provisioning are governed by Bangladesh Bank (BB) through its regulatory circulars. However, the current system follows an incurred loss model rather than the expected credit loss (ECL) model outlined in IFRS 9. International organizations, including the IMF, have expressed concerns over loan classification practices in Bangladesh's banking sector, cited their tendency to understate Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratios. In response, Bangladesh Bank issued a roadmap for the implementation of ECL-based loan classification and provisioning under IFRS 9, as outlined in BRPD Circular No. 03 dated January 23, 2025. This framework will replace the existing incurred-loss model for loan classification and provisioning by December 2027, with the goal of improving credit risk assessment and the accuracy of financial reporting. This article explores the current loan classification and provisioning practices, highlights their shortcomings, outlines the fundamentals of the

Expected Credit Loss (ECL) approach for loan classification and provisioning, discusses potential challenges in implementing ECL-based practices in the Bangladesh banking sector, and suggests possible solutions moving forward.

Loan Classification and Provisioning Practices in the Bangladesh Banking Sector

In Bangladesh, loan classification and provisioning are regulated by Bangladesh Bank (BB) through its circulars, which categorize loans as "Standard", "Special Mention Account", "Sub-standard," "Doubtful," and "Bad/Loss" based on the duration of overdue payments, each with specific provisioning requirements. As per BRPD circulars, Standard and Special Mention Account (SMA) loans are categorized as "Unclassified Loans," requiring banks to maintain general provisions ranging from 0.25% to 2% of the outstanding loan amount, depending on the customer and product categories (e.g., corporate, retail segments, housing finance, and SME). Sub-standard, Doubtful, and Bad/Loss loans are categorized as "Classified Loans," requiring banks to maintain provisions of (5%-20%), (5%-50%), and 100% of the outstanding loan amount, respectively. In addition to these objective criteria, Bangladesh Bank, through BRPD Circular No. 14 dated 23 September 2012, instructed scheduled

banks to classify loans and maintain provisions based on qualitative judgments.

Shortcomings of current loan classifications and provisioning practice

- Compared to international financial reporting standards for loan classification and provisioning, the banking system of Bangladesh follows the incurred loss model rather than the expected credit loss model to determine the status of a classified loan.
- Under IFRS 9, a loan overdue by 30 days is considered to have significantly increased credit risk and is transferred to Stage 2. However, in Bangladesh, the same 30

days overdue period is used to classify a loan as "Unclassified."

- Further, Bangladesh Bank has increased overdue time to define classified loans and show percentage of NPL at lower level in previous regime.
- The current loan classification and provisioning approach does not take forward-looking information into account.

Due to the aforementioned reasons, scheduled banks failed to accurately classify loans and maintain appropriate provisions for disbursed loans. Consequently, the reported percentages of Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) were misleading, prompting the International Monetary Fund (IMF) to

challenge Bangladesh's existing loan classification and provisioning methods. When approving the ongoing \$4.7 billion loan package for Bangladesh in January of last year, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) established several targets, including the implementation of Expected Credit Loss (ECL) based loan classification and provisioning in accordance with IFRS 9.

To meet the IMF's conditions and prepare the banking industry of Bangladesh for the implementation of Expected Credit Loss (ECL)-based loan classification and provisioning, Bangladesh Bank has moved to strengthen loan classification rules. This includes reducing the overdue period for loan classification and provisioning, as outlined in BRPD Circular #15, issued on 27 November 2024. Please note that this circular will take effect from 01 April 2025.

Implementation of ECL-based Loan Classification and Provisioning under IFRS 9

Bangladesh Bank has recently issued roadmap to implement expected credit loss-based loan classification and provisioning under IFRS 9 through BRPD Circular Letter No. 03 dated 23 January 2025. As per this circular, all scheduled banks of Bangladesh are required to begin implementation from March 2025 of expected credit loss-based loan classification and provisions measurement and complete by 2027.

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Table 1: Roadmap of Implementation of IFRS 9; Source: BRPD Circular Letter No. 03 dated 23 January 2025.

Phases	SN.	Particulars	Timeline of	
			Implementation within	Report Submission to BRPD
PHASE-I	1	a) Formation of the 'IFRS 9 Implementation Team' led by the Managing Director (MD)/CEO	Mar-25	Within 15 April 2025
		b) Preparation of the 'Time Bound Action Plan to Implement ECL-based loan classification and provisioning under IFRS 9' duly approved by the Board of Directors (BODs)		
	2	Develop a database preserving required data (e.g. sector wise, borrower wise and loan-nature wise classification percentages, default percentages, loan loss recovery rates, various macroeconomic factors etc.) of borrowers on a monthly basis from January 2022 onwards to calculate ECL.	Jun-25	Within 15 July 2025
	3	Prepare a pre-assessment report on implementation of ECL-based loan classification and provisioning and submit the same to Banking Regulation and Policy Department (BRPD). The report shall include detailed plan for transition from existing rule-based model to ECL model, probable challenges and required actions to implement IFRS 9.	Sep-25	Within 15 October 2025
	4	Conducting training and capacity building programs on ECL-based loan classification and provisioning for all the relevant employees.	Dec-25	Within 15 January 2026
PHASE-II	5	BB will issue guidelines on ECL-based loan classification and provisioning model following BCBS documents and IFRS 9.	January 2026 (by BB)	---
	6	Finalization of automated ECL-based loan classification and provisioning model by banks following the BB guidelines.	Jun-26	Within 15 July 2026
	7	Implement IFRS 9 on a pilot basis in the branches that collectively cover at least 25% of the total loan portfolio of the bank.	Sep-26	Within 15 October 2026
	8	Implement IFRS 9 on a pilot basis in the branches that cover at least 50% of the total loan portfolio of the bank.	Dec-26	Within 15 January 2027
	9	Parallel preparation of financial statements (provisional) on a half yearly basis under IFRS 9 and existing policy.	December 2026 and onwards	Within 15 days of reference date
PHASE-III	10	Implement IFRS 9 on a pilot basis in branches which cover at least 75% of the total loan portfolio of the bank.	Jun-27	Within 15 July 2027
	11	Full Implementation of ECL-based loan classification and provisioning under IFRS 9 on pilot basis	Dec-27	Within 15 January 2028

Expected Credit Losses and Different Approaches for Measurement of Expected Credit Losses

The weighted average of credit losses with the respective risks of a default occurring as the weights as defined in Appendix A of IFRS 9. So, ECL represents a probability-weighted estimate of the difference between the present value of contractual cashflow and present value of cashflows the entity expects to receive over the remaining life of the financial instrument.

Paragraph 5.5 of IFRS 9 allows two approaches for the measurement of expected credit losses.

- General Measurement Approach (Three Stages Approach);
- Simplified Measurement Approach

General approach is usually used for measurement of loss allowances for loans, advances, and commitments following three stages since their initial recognition. For measurement of loss allowances on trade and lease receivables, which do not have an IFRS 15 financing element, a simplified approach is usually used. This article will primarily emphasize the general measurement approach (three-stage approach) as relevant to loan classification and measurement of impairment loss on loans within the banking sector of Bangladesh.

Expected Credit Losses under General Measurement Approach

Under this measurement approach, banks and financial institutions are required to assess the stage of the loans and advances and measure expected credit loss accordingly for the next 12-month or lifetime.

As the recognition and measurement of expected credit loss (ECL) will affect the financial statements of banks including profitability, and capital adequacy, it is important to know about key components of ECL. ECL is a principle-based approach and does not recommend any rule-based method for calculation of ECL. So, banks and financial institutions have the option to use different methods e.g. discounted cash flow methods, loss rate methods, probability of defaults methods for computation of impairment loss on loans. However, most banks in other countries use the probability of default (PD) method to calculate expected credit loss on loans and other similar financial assets. Under the probability of default method, expected credit loss (ECL) has been calculated using the following formulas:

For on balance sheet items:

$$ECL = \sum PD \times \sum EAD \times \sum LGD$$

For off balance sheet items:

$$ECL = \sum PD \times \sum EAD \times \sum LGD \times \sum CCF$$

Where;

Probability of Default (PD)

It is the estimation of likelihood that the borrower will default on its obligations when they come due over a given period. The bank can determine PD rate based on the credit loss experienced in the past. The historical PD rate may be

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affected by the different macro-economic factors like GDP growth rate and unemployment rate. In this regard, the bank should adjust the historical PD rate with consideration of fluctuation in relevant macro-economic factors. For example, an increase in unemployment rate may reduce the income of the salaried person which may increase PD rate for retail loan.

Different methods are available for computations of PD (e.g. Gross Flow Rate Method, New Flow Rate Method, Credit Index Method), however banks should choose methodology based on loan portfolio, and data availability. Banks and financial institutions can consider the following factors during computations of PD:

- Using data for the entire business cycle (at least five years);
- Using high quality data (avoid outliers and incorrect data);
- Implementation of a single system to record and preserve data to ensure smooth integration of borrower data.

Apart from the above factors, banks are recommended to conduct comprehensive data assessments to ensure high quality and complete data which are required to calculate of PD.

Exposure at Default (EAD)

It means the maximum amount

the borrower can default. Generally, it includes principal outstanding, accrued interest, and future interest that bank is expected to receive under the contract. Practically, EAD is determined based on payment terms, tenures of exposures (Loans / advances), and the point of time at which default of borrower is expected. For defaulted borrowers, outstanding amount (principal amount + accrued interest) at point of time is considered as Exposure at Default (EAD). Exposure at Default (EAD) should be determined for performing borrowers with consideration of the following elements:

- Projected cashflow till the estimated defaulted point;
- Time horizon over which EAD needs to be determined;
- Residual Maturity;
- Macro-economic factors.

Loss Given Default (LGD)

The maximum loss that a bank can suffer in the case of non-repayment of the loans. LGD is calculated as, 1 minus the post default recovery rate which is the percentage of amount recovered out of the total outstanding. Post default recovery can be made using any cash collateral, sale of security pledged or mortgaged with the bank. Like PD and EAD, forward looking information should be considered during calculation of LGD. The following factors

should be taken into account when calculating the Loss Given Default (LGD):

- Estimation of future collateral value including sales discount;
- Time of actual realization of collateral;
- Allocation of collateral across all outstanding exposures, where same borrowers have more exposure with the banks;
- Any other cost related to realization of collateral.

Credit Conversion Factor (CCF)

The only difference in the calculation of ECL for the on-balance sheet and off-balance sheet items is the CCF factor. It is a chance of commitment to getting converted into the actual credit. For example, 50% chance that loan commitment may result in the actual disbursement of loans.

12-month ECL and Lifetime ECL

12-month ECL calculation involves the probability of default (PD) occurring in the next 12 months. Lifetime ECL calculation involves the PD occurring in the remaining tenure of the financial asset. 12 months ECL is calculated when the asset is identified in stage 1 and lifetime ECL is calculated when the is identified in stage 2 & 3.

Figure 1: Three Stages Approach of ECL; Source: Author's Developed

Stage-1

Financial assets (Loans and Advances) which have low credit risk are considered as stage-1. 12 Months ECL has been calculated, and interest income is calculated on gross carrying amount of loans in stage-1.

Let's consider an example - Suppose ABC Bank has a 3-year loan receivable from the customer with principal outstanding of BDT 100 million and interest rate of 10% p.a. The current market value of collateral/security pledged is BDT 95 million.

At a reporting date, ABC Bank has assessed that there has been no significant increase in credit risk since the initial recognition. The loan is therefore classified in terms of credit risk under Stage 1. The PD within 12 months has been calculated based on historical data at 2% and LGD is also calculated 5% (1- 95/100). Therefore, the calculation of ECL would be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ECL} &= \sum \text{PD} \times \sum \text{EAD} \times \sum \text{LGD} \\
 &= 2\% \times 100 \times 5\% \\
 &= \text{BDT } 0.10 \text{ million}
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, interest income will be calculated based on gross outstanding loan amount i.e. 10 million (BDT 100 million x10%).

Stage-2

When a substantial increase in credit risk is identified, the Bank recognizes a lifetime expected credit loss (ECL). For example, if a borrower's external credit rating declines from AAA to A+, the company should assess the need to provision for lifetime ECL. Other examples of a significant increase in credit risk may include a decline in the market value of collateral, unfavorable changes in external market or economic conditions, among others. At this stage interest income will still be recognized based on the gross carrying amount of the asset.

At the end of the first year of loan disbursement, ABC Bank identified a significant increase in credit risk since initial recognition. As a result, the loan is classified under Stage 2 for credit risk assessment due to credit rating declines from AAA to A+. Consequently, ABC Bank must calculate the lifetime Expected Credit Loss (ECL). Based on historical data and available forward-looking information, the Probability of Default (PD) is 20%, and the Loss Given Default (LGD) is 5.56% (1 - 85/90). The ECL calculation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{ECL} &= \sum \text{PD} \times \sum \text{EAD} \times \sum \text{LGD} \\
 &= 20\% \times 90 \times 5.56\% \\
 &= \text{BDT } 1 \text{ million}
 \end{aligned}$$

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Here, interest income will be calculated based on gross outstanding loan amount i.e. 9 million (BDT 90 million x10%).

Stage-3

This is the stage at which the loan's credit risk escalates to a level where it is classified as credit-impaired, necessitating the recognition of lifetime expected credit losses (ECL). Additionally, interest income is calculated based on the loan's net carrying amount, which is determined by deducting the loss allowance from the gross carrying amount. A loan is considered credit-impaired when there is an actual default on the due date or when the debtor experiences significant financial distress.

Continuing with the previous example, at the subsequent reporting date, ABC Bank has identified a significant increase in credit risk, evidenced by observed non-repayment

behavior. Additionally, the market value of the collateral has declined to BDT 50 million, while the total loan (principal + interest) outstanding is BDT 80 million. In this context, the recognition of lifetime Expected Credit Loss (ECL) becomes necessary. Moreover, the probability of default (PD) over the remaining life of the asset has been estimated at 40%. This PD indicates a 40% likelihood that the loan will default within the remaining tenure of 2 years (originally 3 years, less 1 year elapsed). Consequently, the calculation of the ECL would be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ECL} &= \Sigma \text{PD} \times \Sigma \text{EAD} \times \Sigma \text{LGD} \\ &= 40\% \times 80 \times (1-50/80)\% \\ &= 40\% \times 80 \times 37.50\% \end{aligned}$$

= BDT 12 million
The interest revenue will be recognized based on the net carrying amount of the loan receivable, which is BDT 68 million (BDT 80

million minus the BDT 12 million ECL provision). Consequently, the interest income will be calculated as BDT 68 million multiplied by 10%, resulting in BDT 6.8 million.

Benefits of Implementation of Expected Credit Loss-based loan Classification and Provisioning under IFRS 9

While the implementation of loan classification and provisioning based on expected credit losses under IFRS 9 is complex and sophisticated, this approach provides several advantages for banks, investors, regulators, and other stakeholders. The key benefits are outlined below:

Timely Recognition of Impairment Loss on Loans and Advances

ECL-based provisioning requires earlier recognition of impairment loss on loans and advances rather than waiting for an actual default. Moreover, as IFRS 9 requires incorporating forward looking information (macro-economic factors) during calculation of Expected Credit Loss, ECL accounting ensures more alignment with economic reality. This approach provides a more accurate and comprehensive assessment of credit losses and financial asset values, requiring banks to increase provisions compared to the current method, thereby reducing the net asset value of loan portfolios.

Ensure Transparency

Under the loss-incurred model, banks may delay recognizing loan impairments, increasing the risk of window dressing and reducing transparency in loan provisioning. The Expected Credit Loss (ECL) model addresses this by ensuring timely recognition through continuous adjustments based on borrower data and forward-looking information.

Improve Comparability

Since most scheduled banks in Bangladesh, except MNC-based banks, follow Bangladesh Bank's guidelines for loan classification and provisioning instead of IFRS

9, their financial statements lack global comparability. Implementing IFRS 9 would enhance the global comparability and acceptability of these banks' financial statements. Enhanced comparability will boost stakeholder confidence, including investors, in financial decision-making.

Key Challenges in Implementation of Expected Credit Loss-based loan Classification and Provisioning under IFRS 9 in the Bangladesh Banking Sector

Although Bangladesh Bank has issued roadmaps to implement

expected credit loss-based loan classification and provision under the IFRS 9, the implementation of the same has several challenges. These challenges are outlined below:

Data Availability and Quality

The Expected Credit Loss (ECL) model requires historical data on customer defaults, past dues, loan segmentation, and creditworthiness. To address this, Bangladesh Bank instructed scheduled banks to compile borrower data monthly from January 2022 onward. However, some scheduled banks in Bangladesh may lack the necessary historical data for effective ECL implementation.

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Regulatory and Supervisory Challenges

Bangladesh Bank has outlined a roadmap for implementing Expected Credit Loss (ECL)-based loan classification and provisioning; however, detailed guidelines have not yet been issued. Without detailed guidance, the commercial banks may face confusion during reviewing internal systems and procedures, technical aspects, and existing capacity which requires for implementation of ECL.

Model Development and Validation

Calculation of Expected Credit Loss under IFRS 9 requires development of advance model (PD, EAD, LGD), which requires

statistical skilled professionals. Due to lack of skilled statistical professionals and risk analytics professionals, some banks may face difficulties developing ECL. Moreover, banks may face challenges during the test of reliability and dependency of the model.

Macroeconomic Information Forecasting Challenges

Reliable and authentic forward looking macroeconomic information (e.g. inflation rate, unemployment rate, GDP growth rate, sector wise export growth rate) are scarce in Bangladesh. As a result, scheduled banks of Bangladesh may not consider forward looking information during calculation of ECL without undue cost and effort.

IT Infrastructure and System Readiness

Most of the banks in Bangladesh currently use spreadsheet to calculate provision on loans. It will be difficult to calculate ECL with manual system as ECL requires development of complex statistical models. Further, banks may face challenges during integration of core banking systems and financial reporting systems. Additionally, existing core banking systems (such as Infosys and Oracle) may need to be modified through change requests to vendors, resulting in additional costs.

Way Forward to Overcome Challenges in Implementation of Expected Credit Loss-based Loan Classification and Provisioning under IFRS 9 in the Bangladesh Banking Sector

Following strategic initiatives can be taken by the banks, regulators, and other stakeholders to ensure successful implementation of expected credit loss-based loan classification and provisioning under IFRS 9 in the Bangladesh Banking Sector by 2027:

Develop Centralized Credit Database and Ensure Automation

Bangladesh Bank can take initiatives through collaboration with scheduled banks to develop centralized database where customer credit worthiness,

historic loss rates, default pattern, and macroeconomics linkage will be available. Scheduled banks of Bangladesh should improve their internal credit risk database ensuring consistency and completeness.

Strengthen Model Development and Validation

Bank should develop robust credit risk modeling techniques to ensure accurate derivation of Probability of Default (PD), Loss Given Default (LGD), and Exposure at Default (EAD). With response to strengthening model development and validation, credit risk management team should be trained on statistical modeling, stress testing and scenario analysis. After development of ECL model, the bank should take initiative to validate the model by independent expert.

Improve Macroeconomic Forecasting

Bangladesh Bank and commercial banks should work together to develop reliable

forward-looking macroeconomic information. In this regard, a sophisticated system should be developed where real time information will be available to conduct stress testing and scenario analysis. Apart from this, scheduled banks should be ready for conducting scenario (optimistic, baseline, and worst) based forecasting.

Upgrade IT Infrastructure and System Readiness

Banks need to invest huge amounts of money to upgrade core banking systems which will support integration of ECL calculation engine. Apart from this commercial bank should improve cybersecurity to protect sensitive information of the customers as well as countries.

Regulatory and Supervisory Enhancements

Bangladesh Bank should issue detailed guidelines on implementation of ECL based loan classification and

provisioning with consideration of BASEL III requirements. Bangladesh Bank should take arrange regular dialogue with different stakeholders like SEC, banks, auditors, public accountants, financial analyst to address emerging implementation challenges.

Training, Awareness, and Change Management

Commercial Banks should arrange a regular training session on expected credit loss approach under IFRS 9 for its officials. Apart from this, cross functional collaboration is required between the Finance, Credit Risk Management, IT, Internal Control and Compliance Team. Bangladesh Bank should improve its on-site and off-site supervision team by arranging necessary training on IFRS 9. Further, professional accounting bodies like ICAB and ICMA should arrange effective CPD seminars, training, and dialogue to improve professional competence of their members.

Conclusion

The implementation of Expected Credit Loss (ECL)-based loan classification and provisioning under IFRS 9 represents a significant shift in the banking sector of Bangladesh, aligning it with global best practices. While this transition offers numerous benefits, such as timely recognition of impairment losses, enhanced transparency, and improved investor confidence, it also presents

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several challenges. These include data availability and quality, the need for skilled professionals in model development, and limitations in macroeconomic forecasting. However, by adopting strategic measures like developing a centralized credit database, strengthening model validation, improving macroeconomic forecasting, and upgrading IT infrastructure, these challenges can be mitigated. The proactive engagement of all stakeholders, including regulators, banks, and professional bodies, will be essential for the successful implementation of IFRS 9 by 2027. This shift not only ensures better alignment with economic realities but also enhances the robustness of the banking sector's credit risk management framework.

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